

Study of Gafur Gulom's work in America

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Abstract. This article provides information about Gafur Ghulam's sharp pen and creative path. It also discusses the study of the writer's work by American writers and the translation of his poems into English.

Keywords: Gafur Ghulam, philosopher, poet, prose writer, "On the Paths of Turksib", translation,

Gafur Gulom, born in 1903 in the Korgontegi neighborhood of Tashkent, was a scientist, poet and writer who could listen to the hearts of our nation and all well-intentioned humanity, and felt their pain from the heart. A rare talent, academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, philosopher, poet, and prose writer, Gafur Gulom left us a significant part of his creative heritage, especially his short stories. Studying these short stories from the perspective of the era and personality is of great importance in educating young people and forming a spirit of respect for their ancestors, and in developing aesthetic taste based on studying artistic interpretations of the 20th century reality from a new perspective. Gafur Gulom was recognized during his lifetime as one of the encyclopedic scholars of the 20th century. But since Gafur Ghulam was, first of all, one of the great poets of the 20th century, we enjoyed the fruits of his poetic talent more and did not rush to study his scientific and journalistic heritage in a special way. Today, when the second "golden age" of our national literature - 20th-century Uzbek literature - has ended and the examples of this literature are being weighed in the balance of history, a deeper look at Gafur Ghulam's treasure of knowledge and paying attention to the precious gems in this treasure will help determine Gafur Ghulam's place in 20th-century world literature. The study and application of Gafur Ghulam's artistic heritage has always been the focus of attention of literary critics and patriots. Examples of creativity were included in the programs of schools and universities as early as the 30s. His works have served to educate people with a broad worldview and independent thinking to this day.

The 1930s hold a special place in world history. During this period, the number of writers coming to our country from abroad increased. Among them was the young Langston Hughes (1902-1967). Langston Hughes was a poet, prose writer, playwright, and publicist. He was born in the US state of Missouri. L. Hughes came to the former Soviet Union in the fall of 1932 with a delegation of thirty-two people. He translated Gafur Ghulam's poem "On the Paths of Turksib" into English. All writers and The works of poets created in the 1930s reflect that era and the life of the people. Gafur Ghulam's poem "On the Paths of Turksib" (1930) is a product of the 1930s, and in the poem, based on the characteristics of the system, the life of the people in the past consisted only of hunger, nakedness, humiliation, and poverty. Gafur Ghulam also could not go beyond the politics and demands of the era. However, it should be noted that the construction of such structures of the era as the Turkestan-Siberian Railway played an important role in the life of the Uzbek people. It is this process that was artistically embodied by Ghulam in the example of creativity. It is worth noting that this road had a positive significance for the fate of the peoples of Central Asia. G.Ghulam's poem "On the Paths of Turksib" begins with the following lines:

These roads

are many ancient roads...

L.Hughes' English translation:

Very old

Immemorially old

Is this road.

As can be seen, L.Hughes fully understood the meaning of this introduction, that is, the first lines of the poem, and their place in the work, and was able to clearly convey it in the translation.

The East has attracted writers from different countries with its rich history and culture. This is due not only to the fact that the East differs from the West in many ways, but also to its rich spiritual and moral potential. This strongly encourages the people of the pen to create. The unique phenomenon of the Eastern Renaissance will continue to inspire writers for many years to come.

Showing that Uzbekistan, with its history and culture, has attracted and continues to attract the attention of many writers, will form in us a deep sense of respect not only for our homeland, but also for Western culture, which will greatly contribute to educating our people in the spirit of universal humanity. It will also encourage scientists to actively study our cultural heritage of the past.

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